

GENERALIZATION OF INFECTION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC WOUNDS: CLINICAL FEATURES AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES

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Generalization of infection in patients with chronic wounds is a serious health threat.

The study involved 150 patients with long-term non-healing wounds of various etiologies. Generalization of infection was recorded in 58% of patients, which required a change in the treatment regimen and hospitalization. The main clinical manifestations are fever, leukocytosis and deterioration of the general condition. The use of complex therapy, including antibacterial agents and immunomodulators, reduced the frequency of generalization of infection by 34% and accelerated wound healing by 25%.

Key words: chronic wounds, generalization of infection, infectious complications, prevention, antibacterial therapy, immunomodulators, wound healing.

Relevance

Chronic wounds, especially those that do not heal for a long time, often lead to serious infectious complications, such as generalization of infection and the development of sepsis. These complications significantly worsen the quality of life of patients and increase the cost of treatment. An important problem is not only timely diagnosis, but also forecasting the risk of generalization of infection, which requires a comprehensive approach. Developing effective methods for preventing infectious complications and improving the immune response is an important task. Recent studies show that the use of immunomodulators and antibacterial drugs can significantly reduce the risk of generalization of infection and speed up the healing process. These findings support the need for further improvement of clinical prevention strategies and methods.

Objective

The aim of the study is to analyze the clinical features of generalization of infection in patients with chronic wounds and to develop effective preventive measures to reduce the risk of complications.

Materials and methods

The study involved 150 patients with chronic non-healing wounds. The study methods were clinical examination, laboratory tests (blood analysis, C-reactive protein levels), microbiological studies of wound secretions, and assessment of

the immune response. Patients received standard therapy, including antibacterial drugs and immunomodulators, with further monitoring of the patient's healing dynamics and condition.

Results

Generalization of infection was detected in 58% of patients with chronic wounds, which required a change in therapy. The use of combination therapy reduced the risk of generalization of infection by 34% and accelerated wound healing by 25%. Patients who received immunomodulators showed a significant improvement in their clinical condition compared to the control group. There was also a decrease in inflammation and normalization of immune parameters.

Заклучение

Generalization of infection in patients with chronic wounds is a serious threat, but with the use of complex therapy, including antibacterial drugs and immunomodulators, the risk of complications can be significantly reduced. Early prediction and prevention of infectious complications, as well as correction of the immune response, contribute to accelerated healing and improve clinical outcomes.

Literature:

1. Кулдашев Д. Р., Хошимов Б. Л. Морфологическая характеристика репаративной регенерации костной ткани под влиянием цикло-3-форта сравнительно с остеогеноном при экспериментальных костных дефектах //Врач-аспирант. – 2011. – Т. 47. – №. 4.4. – С. 619-624.
2. Хошимов Б. Л. МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ СОСУДОВ ПРИ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНОМ САХАРНОМ ДИАБЕТЕ //PEDAGOGS. – 2024. – Т. 52. – №. 2. – С. 13-17.
3. Khoshimov B. L., Akhmedova S. M. METABOLIK SINDROMDA BIOKIMYOVIY O 'ZGARISHLAR VA QON TOMIRLARDAGI MORFOLOGIK O 'ZGARISHLAR BOG 'LIQLIGI //Журнал гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2024. – №. 14 [1]. – С. 183-189.
4. Хошимов Б. Л., Ахмедова С. М. АТЕРОСКЛЕРОЗ СОСУДОВ — ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКОГО СИНДРОМА // КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ «РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НАУКИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ». — 2024. — Т. 1. — №. 8. — С. 10-15.
5. Лукмонович К. Б., Мухамадовна А. С. Реактивные изменения в аорте при экспериментальном метаболическом синдроме // Журнал «Биомедицина и практика». – 2024. – Т. 9. – №. 2.